

The Role of Generative AI in Education: Perceptions of Saudi students

Background: Generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) tools have reshaped education by opening new horizons for more efficient educational practices. With the advent of these innovations, it has become essential to engage students by revealing their perceptions, especially as they are key stakeholders who play a pivotal role in the success of integration, development, and policy implementation processes.

Purpose: This study aims to provide an analysis of students' perceptions of the role of GenAI tools through five axes: 1) level of knowledge and awareness; 2) level of acceptance and readiness; 3) the role of GenAI in education; 4) level of awareness of potential concerns and challenges; and 5) The impact of GenAI tools on achieving the Sustainable Development Goals in education. Methods: A quantitative survey of 1390 students from 15 Saudi universities. Results: Students had positive perceptions of the GenAI in education. A relationship exists between students' perceptions of GenAI and their scientific specializations, as students in computer sciences showed greater awareness regarding concerns and challenges, whereas students in agricultural sciences showed greater awareness of the impact of GenAI tools on Sustainable Development Goals. The results also indicated a worrying trend in which participants did not pay enough attention to the importance of following ethical standards when using GenAI tools. Conclusions: The study offers valuable insights on GenAI adoption in higher education, there is an urgent need to consider developing appropriate use policies, spreading awareness, and creating systems capable of detecting unethical cases. Value: As studies on this field remain comparatively scarce, the study results contribute to further discussion on developing successful integration methods and adopting appropriate usage policies.